

Factors Influencing the Acceptance of Augmented Reality in Young E-Consumers' Decisions: Insights from Cross-Countries Qualitative Research

Małgorzata BARTOSIK-PURGAT, Monika GUZEK, Wiktoria RAKOWSKA, Patricia BALBOA, Ryne A. JOHNSON, Tomasz GRZEGORCZYK

Poznań University of Economics and Business

Abstract

Purpose: to answer research questions about the significance of motives and risks affecting the acceptance of AR technologies by young e-commerce consumers in Poland, South Korea, and the United States.

Methodology: The research methods are twofold. First, a narrative literature review was conducted to identify the main motives and risks concerning AR acceptance in e-commerce. Second, focus group interviews were conducted in Poland, South Korea, and the United States, involving an experiment. The qualitative analysis was applied using MAXQDA.

Findings: The main findings show the similarities and differences among researched groups. Moreover, new motivators and risks were identified that have not been emphasised often in the literature so far. For example, information performance can be added as a factor influencing AR use in e-commerce. In the group of risks, there are health concerns that sitting at home and buying online with AR can affect people's mental health. Moreover, concerns are identified about young people's lack of willingness and ability to communicate and form relationships.

Originality: The combination of the three aspects, i.e., the acceptance of AR technology in online shopping, the young consumer segment, and countries' diversity, represents a unique contribution to the literature. This originality adds to the existing models regarding consumers' acceptance of new technologies (e.g., TAM, UTAUT, UTAUT2).

Practical implications: Young shoppers' knowledge of the factors that determine and enhance the use of AR in e-commerce is of great practical importance for online shops.

Keywords: Augmented Reality; e-commerce, young consumers, qualitative research

This research was funded by the National Science Centre (Poland), grant no. 2022/47/B/HS4/00448, titled "Determinants of young consumers' acceptance of the use of augmented reality in e-commerce—a cross-cultural perspective."

This research was partially supported by funds granted by the Minister of Science of the Republic of Poland under the „Regional Initiative for Excellence” Programme for the implementation of the project “The Poznań University of Economics and Business for Economy 5.0: Regional Initiative – Global Effects (RIGE)”.

Introduction

The advent of cutting-edge technologies, including artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and augmented reality, has revolutionised various sectors of the global economy (Kang et al., 2023; Dogra et al., 2023; Aydin, 2023; Rauschnabel et al., 2024). These innovations have not only transformed fields like medicine, entertainment, education, marketing, tourism, and culture but also e-commerce (e.g., Wu & Lai, 2021; Faqih, 2022; Jayaswal & Parida, 2023; tom Dieck et al., 2024). Interactive technologies are reshaping the landscape, thus enhancing the competitiveness of both local and international retailers in the realm of e-commerce (Caboni & Hagberg, 2019; Ho et al., 2023; Dogra et al., 2023). The extent of their adoption by companies is not solely determined by market forces. The consumers' behaviour of these products and services plays a pivotal role (Ho et al., 2023; Pathak & Prakash, 2023). The theoretical models and findings of the empirical research consider diverse motives that have mainly positive impact on the consumer's acceptance of new technologies (e.g., Davis, 1989; Venkatesh et al., 2012; Riar et al., 2022; Ho et al., 2023; Pathak & Prakash, 2023; Wu & Liu, 2023; Çalışkan et al., 2023; Srivastava et al., 2024). There are not only motives but also some risks associated with new technology use that impact the consumers' acceptance (e.g., Zheng & Li, 2023; Azhar et al., 2023).

Age, gender, technological experience, and cultural background play a significant role among e-commerce customers across the various factors that shape the acceptance of new technologies (except motives and risks) (e.g., Abed, 2021; Çalışkan et al., 2023; Aydin, 2023). Age is a particularly crucial determinant of consumers' behaviour towards new technology use (Arachchi & Samarasinghe, 2024; Srivastava et al., 2024), and this study focuses on the young consumer segment (generation Z, which refers to people born between 1995 and 2012). An analysis of this segment reveals that they are more open to new technologies than older generations (Bartosik-Purgat et al., 2022; Taha et al., 2024; Park et al., 2024). When it comes to shopping, they are much more willing to use modern devices that allow them to save time, which they can allocate to other activities such as education, shopping, entertainment or sports (Bartosik-Purgat et al., 2022; Aydin, 2023; Arachchi & Samarasinghe, 2024). The characteristics of young people regarding online shopping are, indeed, because they were born and grew up in the era of rapid Internet development and various tools allowing them to use it, e.g. smartphones, tablets or smartwatches. Another distinguishing feature of Generation Z is its ability to move freely and function in two worlds simultaneously, online

and offline (Jung et al., 2024). Their preferences and behaviours shape the future of e-commerce, making it crucial for marketers to understand and adapt to their needs (Bartosik-Purgat et al., 2022; Park et al., 2024).

New technologies have opened up a world of possibilities for consumers, offering them novel and captivating solutions (Pesonen & Horster, 2012). Among these, Pine and Gilmore (2014) identify the fusion of digital technology with reality as a critical driver of progress in the experience economy. This fusion, a concept brought to life by augmented reality (AR), is a revolutionary introduction in the context of e-commerce. AR seamlessly blends real-world images with computer graphics and 3D animations (Azuma, 1997; Correia et al., 2020; Kumar, 2022), creating a unique connection between the physical and digital realms. Unlike virtual reality, which isolates users in a simulated environment, AR enhances the real world, making products and services more appealing and user-friendly (Dogra et al., 2023). Interaction with an AR system offers a more immersive experience (e.g. Neuhofer et al., 2013; Javornik et al., 2016; Correia et al., 2020; Riar et al., 2022) than traditional reality, deepening the consumer's engagement and potentially influencing their purchasing decisions.

Augmented reality (AR) is one of the digital technologies that could be considered impactful in redefining the concept of retail stores. AR is shaping a new space where physical and augmented/virtual objects are integrated (Flavián et al., 2019; Kumar, 2022; Riar et al., 2022). Increasingly, retailers rely on interactive technologies to improve consumers' shopping experiences (Rese et al., 2017; Jayaswal & Parida, 2023; Recalde et al., 2024).

Despite the vast possibilities of AR application and its advantages (e.g., better product selection, fewer online shopping returns), AR is still not widespread in e-commerce (Recalde et al., 2023). This results from the high costs of AR implementation and the uncertainty linked to consumers' acceptance of new technologies concerning the privacy aspects, limitations in the devices used by consumers and even education about advantages connected with AR use (Ryan, 2021). There is a need to investigate what drives consumers to use/or not use AR technology in online shopping. After the COVID-19 pandemic and its immediate aftermath, the e-commerce sector is likely to develop (Billewar et al., 2022; Romano et al., 2022; Jayaswal & Parida, 2023; Recalde et al., 2024). Consumers may prefer buying products online rather than shopping in crowded shopping malls. In Kissler et al.'s (2020) prediction of different scenarios of post-pandemic behaviour, one of the main conclusions is that people should maintain social distancing over a long time. AR technology allows consumers to mitigate the drawbacks of online shopping by allowing them to try on the product by showing a pair of glasses on a

consumer's face or displaying how a new wardrobe fits in the bedroom (Rese et al., 2017; Jayaswal & Parida, 2023).

The article's main objective is to answer research questions (RQs) about the significance of factors, not only motives but also risks, affecting the acceptance of AR technologies (interpreted as an intention to use) by young e-commerce consumers in different countries. We have chosen three culturally, economically, and technologically diverse countries: South Korea, Poland, and the United States. The combination of the three aspects, i.e., the acceptance of AR technology in online shopping (motives and risks), the young consumer segment, and countries' diversity, represents a gap in the literature. This is our main contribution and the novelty to the knowledge concerning the existing models towards the consumers' acceptance of new technologies (e.g., TAM, UTAUT, UTAUT2).

The primary research methods used in the paper are twofold. First, a narrative literature review was conducted to identify the main motives and risks concerning AR acceptance in online shopping. These findings allowed us to formulate RQs. Second, focus group interviews (FGI), with an experiment involved, were conducted in three countries to compare the results with the existing literature and models. Then, the qualitative analysis was applied using MAXQDA.

Theoretical background and RQs development

The theoretical background of the research refers to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) and its subsequent developments, such as the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (and UTAUT2), and the theory of perceived value. According to UTAUT2, technology acceptance is determined by performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, hedonic motivation, price value, and habit while being moderated by gender and experience (Venkatesh et al., 2012; Riar et al., 2022). Many studies lately have not directly used TAM and its successors to study the acceptance of a particular technology but rather combine them with other theories and variables (e.g., Romano et al., 2022). We decided to follow this approach as it allows us to consider the characteristics of a specific innovation. The perceived value concept suggests that consumers evaluate products or services based on their perception of the value they will receive. It emphasises that the value of a product or service is not solely determined by its intrinsic characteristics, such as price or quality, but also by the subjective perception of the consumer

(Zeithaml, 1988; Boksberger & Melsen, 2011). One of the main ideas behind the latter is that perceived value consists of both benefits and costs (Zeithaml, 1988; Trivedi et al., 2022).

Consequently, we decided to introduce factors from the UTAUT2 model, such as hedonic motivation, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, and elements negatively influencing user acceptance in our study. To that aim, we used the concept of perceived risk, which is “the expectation of losses associated with the purchase and acts as an inhibitor to purchase behaviour” (Peter & Ryan, 1976, p. 185). Incorporating the theories of perceived value and perceived risk into the theoretical base of our RQs has a tangible benefit. Based on this analysis, we formulated the first RQ1: *What factors, motives and risks, are significant for young consumers' acceptance of AR in e-commerce?*

Hedonic motivation stems from UTAUT2 and measures the degree to which users perceive using AR in e-commerce as enjoyable. Previous research showed that it plays a significant role in accepting various technologies (e.g. Ingham et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2020; Aydin, 2023). In the area of AR research, hedonic motivation and similar factors (e.g. enjoyment) have been confirmed to influence AR's acceptance in e-commerce (e.g. Hilken et al., 2017; Rese et al., 2017; Yim et al., 2017; Trivedi et al., 2022). On this basis, we formulated RQ1a: *Is hedonic motivation significant for young consumers' acceptance of AR in e-commerce?*

The next element included in the theories referred to earlier is effort expectancy, which measures how easy AR use in e-commerce is (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Consumers often resist new, undiffuse technologies due to their fear of lack of technological proficiency. The role of ease of use in accepting various technologies has been confirmed multiple times (e.g., Yen & Wu, 2016; Su et al., 2018; Srivastava et al., 2024; Taha et al., 2024). Research on AR acceptance in this context is still a topical field of study. The significance of ease of AR use was confirmed by e.g. Huang and Liao (2015), Rese et al. (2017), Spreer and Kallweit (2014), and Recalde et al. (2024). We formulated RQ1b: *Is effort expectancy significant for young consumers' acceptance of AR in e-commerce?*

Performance expectancy stems from UTAUT2 as a counterpart of perceived usefulness from TAM. The performance expectancy factor answers the question of consumers deeming AR as applicable, worthy of their attention, and improving their productivity (Recalde et al., 2024). While many of the research (e.g. Hilken et al., 2017; Rese et al., 2017; Yim et al., 2017; Kumar, 2022; Srivastava et al., 2024) found that the utilitarian aspect of AR was one of the most critical predictors of AR acceptance in e-commerce, Bonnin's study (2020) presented surprisingly

mixed findings: in study 1 it had a low influence, while in study 2 no influence. This underlines the need for further studies. We believe that AR's application in e-commerce brings significant functional benefits to consumers, which they consider, and that is why we have formulated the next RQ1c: *Is performance expectancy significant for young consumers' acceptance of AR in e-commerce?*

Research findings of acceptance models of various technological innovations showed that perceived risk has a negative effect on acceptance (e.g. Martins et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2016). Research on the perceived risk in terms of AR is scarce, as only its product/service and privacy dimensions were analysed in single studies (e.g., Azhar et al., 2023). Bonnin (2020) found that perceived product risk negatively influences the attractiveness of AR stores and their patronage intention. These findings are interesting as AR is a tool to decrease the risk of unwanted online purchases by giving one a better sense of product features and their fit (Beck & Crié, 2018). We believe that similar results can be achieved when analysing the influence of perceived AR risk on AR's e-commerce acceptance. We define perceived AR-driven purchase risk as the risk of not being satisfied with the product purchased in an online store evaluated using AR. That is why we want to find out (RQ1d) *if perceived AR-driven purchase risk is significant for consumers' acceptance of AR in e-commerce.*

Another dimension of perceived risk is vulnerability regarding the possible loss of consumers' personal information (data privacy risk). Research on various technological innovations (e.g., Gao et al., 2015) has shown that this factor may negatively influence technology acceptance. AR's required use of a device camera (e.g., laptop, smartphone, etc.) for facial recognition and spatial tracking makes it a target for attacks on data security, given the amount of data being transmitted and stored. Consumer concerns about marketers collecting and using personal data seem relevant (Martin et al., 2017; Ryan, 2021), particularly concerning AR technologies (Dacko, 2016). Some authors state that consumers' awareness of privacy practices influences their decision-making process regarding online shopping with AR use (Hilken et al., 2017; Ryan, 2021). There is a scientific debate on the privacy paradox: while online consumers are concerned about their privacy, they fail to take adequate precautions or abstain from disclosing information (Bandara et al., 2020). In terms of AR, it is still unknown if consumers are generally aware of privacy risks and, if yes, whether they care to such an extent that it would influence AR's acceptance. That is why we have formulated the RQ1e *if perceived privacy risk is significant for young consumers' acceptance of AR in e-commerce.*

Research indicates connections between cultural factors and various consumer behaviours linked to adopting developing technologies (Bartosik-Purgat & Grzegorzcyk, 2024). Some scholars have identified correlations between cultural influences and activities such as mobile banking (Kumar et al., 2023; Wu & Liu, 2023), utilisation of robotics (Castelo & Sarvary, 2022), engagement in m- and s-commerce (Hung & Chou, 2014; Jadir et al., 2023), as well as general attitudes and acceptance of new technology (Jung et al., 2023; Wu & Liu, 2023). Jung et al. (2018) conducted one of the broadest studies on AR adoption influenced by cultural heritage tourism. They concluded that cultural variations had a significant role in adopting AR technology. Research on the influence of cultural characteristics on the adoption of AR technology is still only infrequently conducted, and as a result, the literature on the topic is limited (Bartosik-Purgat & Grzegorzcyk, 2024). That is why we have formulated an RQ2: *Are there any differences in the significance of motives and risks of AR acceptance in e-commerce among young consumers from diverse countries?*

Research method

After the narrative literature review based on Emerald and Science Direct databases and the formulation of RQs, we have decided to use the qualitative approach to describe and understand the factors impacting the consumers' acceptance of AR technology in e-commerce among young participants from different countries (Craig & Douglas, 2009; Braun & Clarke, 2013). Focus group interviews (FGIs) with the element of the experiment were conducted in Poland, South Korea and the United States to achieve the answers to RQs. The authors obtained permission from the Ethical Commission at the University where the research was conducted.

The FGI's focused on a reasonably neutral product bought by both women and men that can be bought online thanks to AR – glasses. Research shows that consumer acceptance of AR technology varies for different products (Recalde et al., 2024). The researched consumer segment belongs to Generation Z (born between 1996 and 2015).

The study focused on WebAR technology, which uses web browsers and the capabilities of mobile and stationary devices to display virtual creations on real-world objects (Jayaswal & Parida, 2023). Users do not need special devices or software to use AR applications because they only require a device with Internet access, a significant advantage for WebAR technologies. WebAR utilises the device camera and adjacent functions (hardware and

software) to track the environment and display virtual objects over the images represented in the camera application.

The FGIs were conducted using the Zoom platform in three groups (Polish, American, and Korean) in February and March 2024, with 6-8 participants in each group purposively selected and meeting age and origin criteria (the authors have benefited from the assistance of university researchers in the respective countries), moderated by one of the research team members. The interviews were conducted based on a pre-prepared focus scenario, which included open-ended questions on factors influencing the acceptance of AR technology (concerning RQs) when purchasing eyeglasses from online shops. The primary basis for preparing the scenario were the theories described above, the models, and the research results of other authors, which were also used to formulate the RQs.

The moderator prefaced the rules of the participant's involvement in the study, its purpose, and the ethics committee approval that the research team received. The moderator invited attendees to a short experiment to familiarise them with AR technology and how to purchase glasses. Participants went to the website of one of the stores indicated by the moderator and tried on the glasses with the AR's use. They continued to participate in a discussion about AR technology use, its motives, and risks. Transcriptions were prepared after the FGI's, and MAXQDA was used for further qualitative analysis.

Following Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach, a thematic analysis was conducted to identify, analyse, and interpret patterns of meaning ('themes') within the qualitative data. The first step involved transcribing the recordings and thoroughly reading and rereading the material to identify initial ideas. Next, the authors systematically analysed the entire data set, coding particular features to generate an initial coding framework. In the third step, we searched for themes by grouping all generated codes into potential thematic clusters. Subsequently, two authors reviewed the themes to ensure they were coherent about the coded extracts and the entire data set. We subsequently defined and named the themes through ongoing analysis, refining the specifics of each theme and the overall narrative and generating clear definitions and names for each theme. In the final step, the authors conducted a comprehensive analysis, relating their findings back to the research question and producing a detailed analysis. The data were analysed based on the cultural background of the interviewees.

The codes were categorised into four main thematic clusters that identified the motivations and risks associated with using AR in e-commerce, the benefits of such a solution, and the impact of AR on the decision-making process during purchasing products online. An

additional thematic cluster was added to determine the level of familiarity with AR technology and the interviewees' engagement in online shopping (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Code tree with the frequency of codes' occurrence

Source: own elaboration in MAXQDA

Thematic analysis of the obtained data indicated differences between the studied groups. Differences in the frequency of occurrence of each code are presented graphically in Figures 2, 3 and 4.

Figure 2. Code cloud of the Polish group

Source: own elaboration in MAXQDA

Figure 3. Code cloud of the Korean group

Source: own elaboration in MAXQDA

Figure 4. Code cloud of the American group

Source: own elaboration in MAXQDA

Results

Experience in online shopping and use of AR

Participants were initially asked about their experiences of online shopping in general and the use of AR (descriptions of abbreviations used in the analysis are as follows, e.g., PW1 – participant no. one in the Polish focus group of women; KW2 – participant no. two in the Korean focus group of women; AW1 – participant no. one in the American focus group of women; PM4 – participant no. four in the Polish focus group of men; KM1 - participant no. one in the Korean focus group of men; AM2 – participant no. two in the American focus group of men).

In the Polish group, most participants indicated they shop online very often (at least once a week). However, almost all participants emphasised unfamiliarity with AR technology and did not use it when shopping.

“I have no experience with AR at all (...) However, when it comes to online shopping, I very often buy things, and it happens once a week”(PM2)

“I also have no experience when it comes to AR. When it comes to online shopping, I think I have quite a bit of experience already...I buy online about once a week.”(PM4)

"I have a lot of experience with online shopping. I order something online at least once a week (...). I am not really familiar with the use of AR"(PM1)

Some Polish participants emphasised that they had seen AR technology on Instagram or Snapchat. Only one person gave the example of a jewellery shop where AR is used.

"I saw it once on Instagram"(PW3). "I will honestly admit that it looks a bit like a Snapchat filter to me."(PM2)

"I have encountered this technology at Pandora. You can just try on rings or bracelets there. This is also a very cool idea."(PW1)

"I once saw on Instagram that some influencers recommended AR apps where you can try on glasses and showed how such an app works."(PW5)

A similar situation was observed in the American group. They are active e-commerce customers with varying frequency.

"I'd say I shop probably 80% of the time online (...) buying probably a couple of things a week."(AW1)

"Personally, I would say I shop about 40% online and 60% in person." (AW2)

Americans mostly indicated a lack of familiarity with AR.

"I'm not too familiar with AR, to be honest."(AM2)

"Neither am I."(AM1)

Some participants identified it with the mobile application Pokémon Go.

"(...) if you guys have heard about the game Pokémon Go, that is essentially AR..."(AW3)

"I've used both Pokémon Go and I've also used a VR virtual reality headset before."(AW1)

AR technology is not widely known in practice among those participants in the Korean group.

"I know there are things like Facebook's Meta Glasses and Apple Glass, but I've never tried them."(KM1)

Some Koreans indicated the use of AR in museums.

"(...) when I visited a museum and they showed some of their statues in AR programming, so I wore the so-called AR glasses. Yeah, I used it."(KW1)

Other Koreans emphasised familiarity with AR from online observations rather than active use of the technology.

"(...) I haven't used it personally, other than like Instagram filters. But I know about it because I saw videos of influencers in the US using it."(KW2)

The other noticed that VR technology is more common in South Korea than AR.

"Well, in my opinion, in Korea, maybe VR is more popular because of some games"(KM1).

In the next section of the interview, participants were subsequently subjected to a short experiment. Their task was to go to the website of an eyewear shop that uses AR technology, select several pairs of glasses, and try them on. After about 10 minutes, the moderator started discussing the participants' experiences using AR technology during the experiment, including motivations and risks.

Hedonic experience

The Polish group indicated a positive experience and good impression of AR technology following the experiment because it provides pleasure and is an intriguing option.

"(...) a pleasure for the users (...) it's new, it's not that common yet, and it attracts the user."(PW4)

"It resembles a Snapchat filter. But overall, the impression is very good."(PM4)

"I am satisfied with this experience - the experiment. I really enjoyed the opportunity to try on different glasses."(PM2)

"I think this kind of virtual try-on is a very cool option."(PW3)

Polish participants emphasised that AR technology is similar to Snapchat filters and that although they will not encounter it in online shops, they know it, and AR doesn't have a "Wow-effect" for them. They also frequently pointed out that AR in online shops can be fun for other consumer groups, both younger than the respondents and older. This may be because they are more familiar with using new media.

"I think it's also cool for older people, maybe around our parents' age. I think such an opportunity will be fun and entertaining for them. It's less fun for us because we use filters a lot, so we're used to it."(PW2)

"If you can call it filters, of those we know from the Snapchat app. And I think it can be fun to try these things on, especially for a younger user, which can later influence the purchase decision."(PM2)

Koreans pointed out that trying on glasses in this way can be good fun but in a group of a few friends.

"I think it's fun. It's not very much fun (...), but when I try it with my friends or someone more likely to enjoy it, I can enjoy more things from the AR program."(KW1).

It was also emphasised that the fun is at the beginning when you are unfamiliar with the technology, the fun tends to pass

"(...) like maybe the first pair was fun because it was like "ohhhhh" something new I can do, but then it was just like normal that I can try it."(KW2)

Many American participants emphasised spontaneously that the experience of using AR was fun.

„I find it fun."(AW1)

"It was fascinating because I've never used this approach before."(AW3)

"I thought it was pretty cool."(AW2)

"(...) an interesting kind of emotion."(AM1)

Effort expectancy

Most participants (especially in the Polish and American groups) emphasised that it is an easy technology to use from an individual customer's perspective.

"I think there is nothing complicated here; it is easy to use."(PM3)

"Everything was intuitive, easy to find, and no major problems existed."(PM1)

"In terms of effort, well, practically none, because all you had to do was click. In fact, I didn't have to put any effort into it."(PM5)

"It's a big convenience that you don't go to the shop, you just sit at home trying it on. Also, it's very easy to use."(PW1)

The US group indicated that AR was easy to use and similar to trying on and seeing oneself in a mirror.

„It's extremely easy to use."(AM1)

„(...) similar to me having to try it in person, looking in the mirror."(AW3)

Performance expectancy

Almost all groups surveyed emphasised convenience as one of the main motives for using AR and its advantages in online shops. Convenience was often understood as the fact that one does not have to leave the house, that many glasses are in one shop, and that one can freely try on a pair of glasses without the presence of a salesperson.

"First and foremost, comfort because I don't have to go to a salon; I can do it at home. The comfort that no one is standing over me. It's not just advising

me; it's like I can try these glasses on myself. It's a bit different to having live contact with a salesperson, but from a customer perspective, I think it's definitely convenient. There's definitely not that pressure of, first of all, time and that the salesperson will push a particular pair of glasses.”(PM5)

“There are a lot of glasses in such a shop, and you can try them on in your own time.”(PW4)

“I find it convenient because instead of going to the shopping mall to try on sunglasses, I can use AR technology at home. This saves time and effort. It motivates me to use products from companies that offer this technology.”(KM1)

“Advantages being staying in the comfort of home.”(AW1)

In each country group, the convenience of using AR when shopping online was often linked to the responses to time savings

“It was definitely a time-saver.”(PW5)

“For me, convenience means not having to go out of my way and being able to save time since I don't have to go out.”(KW3)

“It would be saving time, not having to run to the store to sit there [and] wait.”(AW3)

“I could see it speeding up the timeline a little bit for me.”(AM1)

Providing information

Some Polish participants highlighted the fact that AR provides information about the product, such as how it fits or doesn't fit the customer, the product's attributes, etc., regarding motivations for incorporating AR in online shopping.

“AR gives information about the product because the key thing in choosing glasses is to see how you look in them.”(PM2)

„(...) it did give some greater knowledge of what it might look like.”(PM3)

“AR provides information about the product because I also have all the specifications right away, such as the dimensions, weight (...). When buying in a shop, I would probably have to ask the salesperson because not all the information would be given...”(PM5)

Polish participants also pointed out that AR can aid in purchasing decisions by providing detailed information. They stressed that this is primarily at the initial stage, such as when sifting through the multitude of products available online, and that the final decision is often made in a physical store.

“AR can help with the initial product selection, whereas for me, it's more for patterning. Later, I would try the same on stationary to ensure I liked it. On the other hand, I think I would then spend less time in the stationary showroom.”(PM1) “I also think it's as a pre-selection. It is a very good solution, but I would also prefer to make sure and try on the actual pair.”(PM4)

“I think AR is very helpful in making decisions. Nevertheless, if someone then wants to go to a stationary shop, he/she will know what to look for.”(PW5)

Similar opinions were obtained among Koreans.

“It's not perfect, but it definitely helps me when deciding. You can see if the frame is the type you want. You can see if it's better for your face to wear something more square or a cut eye.”(KW2)

“It was helpful for me (...) I agree, and I also think that detailed aspects of the product's design, including upgrades and specific features, are important, particularly when they are showcased effectively through AR.”(KM1)

The Americans indicated that AR can be useful in making purchasing decisions. It would be even more useful if there was more information about a product's materials, quality, weight, etc.

“AR can definitely influence the decision-making process.”(AM1)

“Yeah, I definitely think it would be...”(AM2)

„I wouldn't feel the need to go in-store if there was more information about the texture and the quality and material.”(AW1)

“I wish I could get a sense of, like, how I don't know heavy or the texture of it's like tight on my face.”(AM3)

Other motivators for using AR

Among the motives for using AR when shopping, one participant in the American group indicated that the technology prevents the transmission of viruses, which can happen in offline shops.

„Nobody is actually touching the glasses, so there's no virus and disease transmission.”(AW1)

Perceived AR-driven purchase risk

Participants in the Polish and Korean groups indicated a concern that the information given on the shop's website regarding the product's material, appearance, and size (e.g. width) may differ and be more limited than it is in reality.

“The sizes of the glasses are given (...) through the camera, it's very difficult to adjust the size of my head and my face (...). In the same way, I would be afraid of the colour reproduction.”(PM1)

“We might like something on the internet, and then in reality it might look different. And then I would be disappointed.”(PW5)

“I think that it is one of the disadvantages because if I get the real one, it might fit differently on my face. That difference from reality? (...) And I would also say that security things like sharing my data are not necessarily well protected.”(KW1)

One Korean highlighted the likelihood of a lack of clear rules regarding the use of AR technology.

"I think there's still room for improvement. I don't believe a clear protocol is established for this technology. We may need to wait for further advancements to ensure better security and reliability."(KM1)

The female US group emphasised that AR does not give the ability to touch (sensory) the product and feel it.

„There's no that sensory input (...)”(AW3)

“(...) feeling it or actually feeling the material it's made out (...) that's the part that's missing.”(AW2)

“You know, when you're looking at glasses in person, you see what you get.”(AW1)

Perceived privacy risk

The main concern about the perceived privacy risks in almost all cultural groups was associated with storing the client's personal data, such as faces, photos from the home, etc., because of the camera`s sharing.

“The risk of sharing images from the flat might be important for someone who has some more valuable things (...)”(PW2)

“One would identify the issue of data protection more as a challenge of this technology.”(PM1)

“There is with regard to the storage of these recordings, but I hope that this is not recorded.”(PM4)

“(...)the AR`s use should be protected by law (...) there should be a message that our image is protected by law and the question is whether we agree to share it.”(PW4)

"(...) risk of somebody hacking your camera, and that's kind of what I was thinking, being safe online"(AW2)

"How can we ensure that our data, what we have in our home, our face shapes and all that isn't being used."(AW1)

"You're at allowing websites to have access to cameras you don't know if they're videotape and you don't know what is going on. If they're saving the data saved, caching."(AM1)

"For me, I think it's like with data storage, you know, because we use it now, and we agree for it to read our face and give it, give us the glasses on our face. But then, how long does it stay in the database? Who has access to that? But is the database actually protected by the government, so it's not possible for anyone to get into it?"(KW2)

"I think there could be issues with digital crime."(KM2)

Other risks and concerns in using AR

The Polish and American groups emphasised a concern that people would become sedentary at home, reluctant to go out, hesitant to interact with other people, and inability to establish relationships could negatively affect the consumers' mental health. the possible need to close down offline shops in the event of the development of AR in e-commerce was also noted.

"People won't leave the house when using AR. They will sit at home in front of the computer, checking everything and looking for product information. Staying at home and not having to leave the house is, to me, a bit of a threat to all of us."(PW1)

"The first thing that comes to my mind is that stationary shops in general will become extinct."(PM5)

“The biggest disadvantage is that we can lose that physical contact with the salesperson, which can be important in the sales process.”(PM2)

„It eliminates the need for human interaction and making the purchase.”(AW3)

The above problem is also presented in terms of AR's advantages. Young people have problems with communication, networking, and building relationships, so this solution may be a good option for them.

“Young people are a bit reluctant to go to a shop and sort of talk to the person selling the glasses there. With AR, many glasses can be tried on without contact with another person. That's maybe the fears that come from COVID-19, and this is just a cool option for people like that (...), and there's no problem that someone's watching, waiting, wants to take care of me, you can do it yourself without any fear of being watched (...). Well, I know just from the pandemic that there are also these problems, such as people being a bit embarrassed to go to the shop, to talk to someone, etc. Maybe not just at our age, but a little bit younger people, this kind of social problem comes up a little bit, so it's a nice option for that kind of people as well.”(PW4)

Discussion and Conclusions

The focus results show that participants shop online with varying frequency albeit without consistent and meaningful AR technology use to date. Individuals indicated familiarity with AR but not with e-commerce. Concerning experience with AR, there were no significant differences between the cross-countries groups studied. Familiarity with AR within the Polish group was indicated to social media such as Snapchat and Instagram while the American group identified it with Pokémon Go.

Differences between the groups were noted concerning hedonic motivation (RQ1a). American participants (especially women) almost all emphasised that AR in e-commerce was fun for them, “pretty cool”, etc. The findings show the importance of hedonic motivation in the use of AR. Similar results were indicated earlier in studies by Hilken et al., 2017 Rese et al., 2017 Yim et al., 2017 and Trivedi et al., 2022. It was indicated in the Korean group that AR in e-commerce could be fun, but with friends and at the beginning of use. In contrast, the Polish group showed less enthusiasm than the others. The Polish group showed less enthusiasm than

the others. Poles indicated it could be more fun for younger and older people than the age of participants. Americans are inherently more positive, with the United States having the highest indulgence rate of those surveyed (Hofstede et al., 2010). Korea is among the most collectivist participants, which is why AR can bring fun to a group of friends.

The results obtained in the FGIs regarding the difficulty of using AR (RQ1b) can be referred to, e.g., Huang and Liao (2015), Rese et al. (2017), Spreer and Kallweit (2014), Ho et al. (2023) and Recalde et al. (2024). In all groups, it was indicated that AR technology is easy to use and intuitive and that it does not take much effort to cope with it. Indeed, the effort expectancy in using AR may contribute to its growing popularity in e-commerce. Otherwise, customers would not use this technology when shopping online.

Many participants across all groups also emphasised that the advantage of AR for them is the convenience and comfort (RQc) of being able to try on as many items as they want at home and at the proper time, in their living room or armchair, that no one (i.e., the salesperson) is standing behind them and asking if they fit or not. The effect of time convenience in AR mobile retailing was also achieved by Chekembayeva et al. (2023). Chekembayeva et al. (2023) also achieved the effect of time convenience in AR mobile retailing. For many young participants, salespeople's presence and involvement are seen as annoying and unhelpful to the sales process.

Regarding the usefulness of AR in e-commerce, the Polish and Korean groups emphasised the importance of providing product information through AR technology and the information available on online shop websites alongside products. Young Poles indicated that AR is useful mainly at the initial purchase decision stage. Informativeness understood as the provision of additional product information, can be an extension of the UTAUT2 model (in the scope of motives influencing the AR use in e-commerce), which was the theoretical basis for the qualitative study design.

Risks in all groups were highlighted as very significant issues. They included the fear of disappointment with the purchased product, i.e. that it will be different in reality than it looked online (AR risk, RQ1d), as well as the risk of sharing and storing personal data (RQ1e). Similar results were found, for example, by Bonnin (2020), Ho et al. (2023). Also, participants in all groups highlighted concerns about whether their data was protected by law and could be used in cybercrimes (Dacko, 2016; Martin et al., 2017; Ryan, 2021; Zheng & Li, 2023).

Referring to RQ2, there were generally no (except for a few) significant differences among surveyed young consumers from different countries regarding attitudes towards AR. This may be due to the homogenisation of young consumers' needs and behaviour regardless

of cultural affiliation. This is undoubtedly influenced by widespread access to the Internet and media, especially the ability to use global entertainment, ease of use of the English language, proficiency in modern communication and media, and consumption of specific brands. These tools (e.g. global media) are shaping the young global consumer as they enable a unification of experiences and needs (Bartosik-Purgat et al., 2022).

Theoretical implications

In a novelty and contribution to the theory, additional motivators and risks may be identified that have not been emphasised often in the literature and models and stem from changes in consumer behaviour related to COVID-19 and young people's engagement with new media. In the group of motivators, information performance can be added as a factor influencing AR use in e-commerce. In the group of risks, there are health concerns that sitting at home in isolation and buying online with AR may negatively affect people's mental health, yet concerns are identified about young people's lack of willingness to socialise, ability to communicate, and capacity to form relationships. Identifying new factors (especially those in the group of risks) that are hardly found in the previous literature leads to significant implications for academia regarding AR use in online shopping.

Besides, an interesting fact is that in the Polish group, on the one hand, the lack of the need to leave home was seen as a plus (great comfort and not having to stress about talking to a salesperson). However, on the other hand, the fear that people would become accustomed to leaving home and interacting with others in general was pointed out (Polish and American groups). In addition, it was pointed out that if AR develops in e-commerce, stationary shops will start to close down. No such concern was indicated in the Korean group.

Practical implications

Knowledge of the factors that determine and enhance the use of AR in e-commerce by young shoppers is of great practical importance. The research indicates that shops offering products aimed at young shoppers should focus on promoting information about using various measures to protect customer data, which respondents particularly highlighted. In addition, it is helpful to provide detailed information about the visual and technical data of the product and to ensure that the product, in reality, is no different than it looks in the online shop. Concerning motives, it is also worth emphasising aspects related to convenience, comfort and a large selection of products. Regarding companies operating internationally, local consumers'

preferences and needs should be researched early, as these may differ between markets (although our study showed no significant differences among groups of young consumers).

The limitations and further research

The primary limitations related to the number of focus groups, the number of participants, and the number of countries can be identified in this study. Further research should attempt to expand the model with the identified new factors, especially in the area of risk, as these may be the primary reason for the low use of AR among e-commerce companies. On the one hand, it would be worth conducting a quantitative study in which the factors identified in this study are assessed. In addition, such a study should also be conducted among age-diverse consumer groups and culturally. Such a study would give more knowledge about adapting services and online shopping sites to customers' needs in different markets. On the other hand, well-designed experiments may be conducted to verify if the consumer knows AR technology because our study showed that most consumers know AR, not from the practice of e-commerce.

References

Abed, S.S. (2021), "Examining augmented reality adoption by consumers with highlights on gender and educational-level differences", *Review of International Business and Strategy*, Vol. 31 No. 3, pp. 397-415. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RIBS-08-2020-0100>.

Abramovich, G. (2020), "How COVID-19 is Impacting Online Shopping Behavior", available at: <https://blog.adobe.com/en/publish/2020/03/26/how-covid-19-is-impacting-online-shopping-behavior> (accessed 20 June 2024).

Arachchi, H.A.D.M. and Samarasinghe, G.D. (2024), "Impact of embedded AI mobile smart speech recognition on consumer attitudes towards AI and purchase intention across Generations X and Y", *European Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 29 No. 1, pp. 3-29. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJMS-03-2023-0019>.

Aydin, G. (2023), "Increasing mobile health application usage among Generation Z members: evidence from the UTAUT model", *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Healthcare Marketing*, Vol. 17 No. 3, pp. 353-379. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPHM-02-2021-0030>.

Azhar, M., Akhtar, M.J., Rahman, M.N. and Khan, F.A. (2023), "Measuring buying intention of generation Z on social networking sites: an application of social commerce adoption model", *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, Vol./No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEAS-02-2022-0047>.

Azuma, R.T. (1997), "A survey of augmented reality", *Presence*, Vol. 6 No. 4, pp. 355-385. <https://doi.org/10.1162/pres.1997.6.4.355>.

Bandara, R., Fernando, M., and Akter, S. (2020), "Explicating the privacy paradox: A qualitative inquiry of online shopping consumers", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, No. 52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.101947>.

Bartosik-Purgat, M. and Grzegorzczuk, T. (2024), "Cross-cultural Adoption of Augmented Reality—Theories and Practices", Bartosik-Purgat, M., Guzek, M. (eds.) *International Business and Culture. Challenges in Cross-Cultural Marketing and Management*, Routledge, New York, pp. 92-107. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781032636962-8>.

- Bartosik-Purgat, M., Jankowska, B. and Mińska-Struzik, E. (2022), „Does Generation Matter for the Use of I4.0 Technologies?” Latukha M. (ed.), *Diversity in action: managing diverse talent in a global economy*, Emerald Publ., pp. 97-120. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80117-226-420221007>.
- Beck, M., and Crié, D. (2018), “I virtually try it...I want it! Virtual Fitting Room: A tool to increase online and offline exploratory behavior, patronage and purchase intentions”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, No. 40, pp. 279-286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2016.08.006>.
- Billewar, S.R., Jadhav, K., Sriram, V.P., Arun, D.A., Mohd Abdul, S., Gulati, K. & Bhasin, D.N.K.K. (2022), “The rise of 3D E-Commerce: online shopping gets real with virtual reality and augmented reality during COVID-19”, *World Journal of Engineering*, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp. 244-253. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WJE-06-2021-0338>.
- Boksberger, P.E., and Melsen, L. (2011), “Perceived value: a critical examination of definitions, concepts and measures for the service industry”, *Journal of Services Marketing*, No. 253, pp. 229-240. <https://doi.org/10.1108/08876041111129209>.
- Bonnin, G. (2020), “The roles of perceived risk, attractiveness of the online store and familiarity with AR in the influence of AR on patronage intention”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, No. 52, 101938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.101938>.
- Braun, V., and Clarke, V. (2006), “Using thematic analysis in psychology”, *Qualitative research in psychology*, Vol. 3 No. 2, pp. 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2013), *Successful Qualitative Research: A Practical Guide for Beginners*, Sage Publ., London.
- Caboni, F., and Hagberg, J.J. (2019), “Augmented reality in retailing: a review of features, applications and value”, *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 47 No. 11, pp. 1125-1140. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-12-2018-0263>.
- Castelo, N., and Sarvary, M. (2022), “Cross-Cultural Differences in Comfort with Humanlike Robots”, *International Journal of Social Robotics*, No. 14, pp. 1865–1873. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-022-00920-y>.
- Chekembayeva, G., Garaus, M. and Schmidt, O. (2023), “The role of time convenience and (anticipated) emotions in AR mobile retailing application adoption”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, No. 72, 103260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2023.103260>.
- Correia Loureiro, S.M., Guerreiro, J. and Ali, F. (2020), “20 years of research on virtual reality and augmented reality in tourism context: A text-mining approach”, *Tourism Management*, No. 77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2019.104028>.
- Craig, C.S., & Douglas, S.P. (2009), *International Marketing Research*, Wiley Publ., Chichester.
- Çalışkan, G., Yayla, İ., and Pamukçu, H. (2023), “The use of augmented reality technologies in tourism businesses from the perspective of UTAUT2”, *European Journal of Innovation Management*, Vol./No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-04-2023-0271>.
- Dacko, S.G. (2017), “Enabling smart retail settings via mobile augmented reality shopping apps”, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, No. 124, pp. 243–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.09.032>.
- Davis, F.D. (1989), “Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology”, *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 13 No. 3, pp. 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Dogra, P., Kaushik, A.K., Kalia, P. and Kaushal, A. (2023), “Influence of augmented reality on shopping behavior”, *Management Decision*, Vol. 61 No. 7, pp. 2073-2098. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-02-2022-0136>.
- Faqih, K.M.S. (2022), “Factors influencing the behavioral intention to adopt a technological innovation from a developing country context: The case of mobile augmented reality games”, *Technology in Society*, No. 69, 101958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2022.101958>.
- Featherman, M.S., and Pavlou, P.A. (2003), “Predicting e-services adoption: a perceived risk facets perspective”, *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, No. 59, pp. 451–474. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1071-5819\(03\)00111-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1071-5819(03)00111-3)
- Flavián, C., Ibáñez-Sánchez, S., and Orús, C. (2019), “The impact of virtual, augmented and mixed reality technologies on the customer experience”, *Journal of Business Research*, No. 100, pp. 547-560 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.10.050>

- Gao, Y., Li, H., and Luo, Y. (2015), "An empirical study of wearable technology acceptance in healthcare", *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Vol. 115 No. 9, pp. 1704–1723. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-03-2015-0087>
- Hilken, T., De Ruyter, K., Chylinski, M., Mahr, D. and Keeling, D.I. (2017), "Augmenting the eye of the beholder: exploring the strategic potential of augmented reality to enhance online service experiences", *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 45 No. 6, pp. 884-905. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-017-0541-x>.
- Ho, J.-Y., Ju, G., Hong, S., An, J. and Lee, C.C. (2023), "Factors influencing customer satisfaction with AR shopping assistant applications in e-commerce: an empirical analysis utilizing text-mining techniques" *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol/No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-03-2023-0089>.
- Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G.J., and Minkov, M. (2010), *Cultures and Organizations; Software of the Mind*, McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Hung, C.L. and Chou, J.C.L. (2014) "Examining the cultural moderation on the acceptance of mobile commerce", *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management*, Vol. 11 No. 2, 1450010. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219877014500102>.
- Huang, T.L. and Liao, S.L. (2017), "Creating e-shopping multisensory flow experience through augmented-reality interactive technology", *Internet Research*, Vol. 27 No. 2, pp. 449-475. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-11-2015-0321>.
- Ingham, J., Cadieux, J. and Mekki Berrada, A. (2015), "e-Shopping acceptance: A qualitative and meta-analytic review", *Information & Management*, Vol. 52 No. 1, pp. 44–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2014.10.002>.
- Jadil, Y., Jeyaraj, A., Dwivedi, Y.K., Rana, N.P., and Sarker, P. (2023), "A meta-analysis of the factors associated with s-commerce intention: Hofstede's cultural dimensions as moderators", *Internet Research*, Vol. 33 No. 6, pp. 2013-2057. <https://doi.org/10.1108/INTR-10-2021-0768>.
- Jayaswal, P. and Parida, B. (2023), "Past, present and future of augmented reality marketing research: a bibliometric and thematic analysis approach", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 57 No. 9, pp. 2237-2289. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-05-2022-0397>.
- Javornik, A. (2016), "Augmented reality: research agenda for studying the impact of its media characteristics on consumer behavior", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, No. 30, pp. 252-261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2016.02.004>.
- Jung, S.D., Claire, S. and Kim, S. (2024), "Gen Z consumers' expectations for smart convenience stores in the USA, South Korea, and Japan", *Young Consumers*, Vol. 25 No. 3, pp. 400-420. <https://doi.org/10.1108/YC-10-2022-1623>.
- Jung, T.H., Lee, H., Chung, N. and tom Dieck, M.C. (2018), "Cross-cultural differences in adopting mobile augmented reality at cultural heritage tourism sites", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 30 No. 3, pp. 1621-1645. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-02-2017-0084>.
- Kang, J.-Y.M., Kim, J.-E., Lee, J.Y. and Lin, S.H. (2023), "How mobile augmented reality digitally transforms the retail sector: examining trust in augmented reality apps and online/offline store patronage intention", *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, Vol. 27 No. 1, pp. 161-181. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMM-12-2020-0273>.
- Kissler, S.M., Tedijanto, Ch., Goldstein, E., Grad, Y.H. and Lipstich, M. (2020), "Projecting the transmission dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 through the postpandemic period", *Science*, Vol. 368 Iss. 6493, pp. 860-868. doi: 10.1126/science.abb5793.
- Kumar, H. (2022), "Augmented reality in online retailing: a systematic review and research agenda", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 50 No. 4, pp. 537-559. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-06-2021-0287>.
- Kumar, P., Chauhan, S., Gupta, P. and Jaiswal, M.P. (2023), "A meta-analysis of trust in mobile banking: the moderating role of cultural dimensions", *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol. 41 No. 6, pp. 1207-1238. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-02-2022-0075>.
- Liu, F., Lim, E.T.K., Li, H., Tan, C.-W. and Cyr, D. (2020), "Disentangling utilitarian and hedonic consumption behavior in online shopping: An expectation disconfirmation perspective", *Information and Management*, 103199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2019.103199>.
- Martin, K. D., Borah, A. and Palmatier, R.W. (2017), "Data privacy: Effects on customer and firm performance", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 81 No. 1, pp. 36–58. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jm.15.0497>.

Martins, C., Oliveira, T. and Popovič, A. (2014), "Understanding the Internet banking adoption: A unified theory of acceptance and use of technology and perceived risk application", *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 34 No. 1, pp. 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2013.06.002>.

Neuhofer, B., Buhalis, D. and Ladkin, A. (2013), "A typology of Technology-Enhanced Tourism Experiences", *International Journal of Tourism Research*, Vol. 16 No. 4, pp. 340-350. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr>.

Park, J., Yoo, J.W., Cho, Y. and Park, H. (2024), "Understanding switching intentions between traditional banks and Internet-only banks among Generation X and Generation Z", *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol./No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-06-2023-0338>.

Pathak, K. and Prakash, G. (2023), "Exploring the role of augmented reality in purchase intention: Through flow and immersive experience", *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, No. 196, 122833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122833>.

Pesonen, J. and Horster, E. (2012), "Near Field Communication Technology in Tourism", *Tourism Management Perspectives*, No. 4, pp. 11-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2012.04.001>.

Peter, J. and Ryan, M. (1976), "An investigation of perceived risk at the brand level", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 13 No. 2, pp. 184-188. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3150856>.

Pine, B.J. and Gilmore, J.H. (2014), "A leader's guide to innovation in the experience economy", *Strategy & Leadership*, Vol. 42 No. 1, pp. 24-29. . <https://doi.org/10.1108/SL-09-2013-0073>.

Rauschnabel, P.A., Felix, R., Heller, J. and Hinsch, C. (2024), "The 4C framework: Towards a holistic understanding of consumer engagement with augmented reality", *Computers in Human Behavior*, No. 154, 108105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.108105>.

Recalde, D., Jai, T.C. and Jones, R.P. (2024), "I can find the right product with AR! The mediation effects of shopper engagement on intent to purchase beauty products", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, No. 78, 103764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2024.103764>.

Rese, A., Baier, D., Geyer-Schulz, A. and Schreiber, S. (2017), "How augmented reality apps are accepted by consumers: A comparative analysis using scales and opinions", *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, No. 124, 306–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.10.010>.

Riar, M., Xi, N., Korbek, J.J., Zarnekow, R. and Hamari, J. (2023), "Using augmented reality for shopping: a framework for AR induced consumer behavior, literature review and future agenda", *Internet Research*, Vol. 33 No. 1, pp. 242-279. <https://doi.org/10.1108/INTR-08-2021-0611>.

Romano, B., Sands, S. and Pallant, J.I. (2022), "Virtual shopping: Segmenting consumer attitudes towards augmented reality as a shopping tool", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 50 No. 10, pp. 1221-1237. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-10-2021-0493>.

Ryan, T., (2021), "What's Holding Consumers Back from Adopting AR/VR Shopping Tech?" RetailWire. available at: <https://retailwire.com/discussion/whats-holding-consumers-back-from-adopting-ar-vr-shopping-tech/>. (accessed 15 June 2024).

Srivastava, S., Mohta, A. and Shunmugasundaram, V. (2024), "Adoption of digital payment FinTech service by Gen Y and Gen Z users: evidence from India", *Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance*, Vol. 26 No. 1, pp. 95-117. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DPRG-07-2023-0110>.

Spreer, P., and Kallweit, K. (2014), "Augmented reality in retail: Assessing the acceptance and potential for multimedia product presentation at the PoS", *Transactions on Marketing Research*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 20–35. <https://doi.org/10.15764/MR.2014.01002>.

Su, P., Wang, L. and Yan, J. (2018), "How users' Internet experience affects the adoption of mobile payment: a mediation model", *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, Vol. 30 No. 2, pp. 186–197. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2017.1297788>.

Qin, H., Peak, D.A. and Prybut, V. (2021), "A virtual market in your pocket: How does mobile augmented reality (MAR) influence consumer decision-making?" *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, No. 58, 102337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102337>.

Taha, S., Kaba, A. and Al-Qeed, M.A. (2024), "Exploring students' perceptions toward the use of augmented reality for digital library services", *Digital Library Perspectives*, Vol. 40 No. 1, pp. 53-66. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLP-06-2023-0053>.

tom Dieck, M.C., Cranmer, E., Prim, A. and Bamford, D. (2024), "Can augmented reality (AR) applications enhance students' experiences? Gratifications, engagement and learning styles",

Information Technology & People, Vol. 37 No. 3, pp. 1251-1278. <https://doi.org/10.1108/itp-10-2021-0823>.

Trivedi, J., Kasilingam, D., Arora, P. and Soni, S. (2022), "The effect of augmented reality in mobile applications on consumers' online impulse purchase intention: the mediating role of perceived value", *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, Vol. 21 No. 4, pp. 896–908. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cb.2047>.

Venkatesh, V., Thong, J.Y.L. and Xu, X. (2012), "Consumer Acceptance and Use of Information Technology: Extending the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 36 No. 1, pp. 157-178. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41410412>.

Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. and Xu, X. (2016), "Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology: A Synthesis and the Road Ahead", *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 17 No. 5, pp. 328–376. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1jais.00428>.

Wu, X. and Lai, I.K., W. (2021), "The acceptance of augmented reality tour app for promoting film-induced tourism: the effect of celebrity involvement and personal innovativeness", *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 454-470. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTT-03-2020-0054>.

Wu, Z. and Liu, Y. (2023), "Exploring country differences in the adoption of mobile payment service: the surprising robustness of the UTAUT2 model", *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol. 41 No. 2, pp. 237-268. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-02-2022-0052>.

Xiong, J., Hsiang, E.-L., He, Z., Zhan, T. and Wu, S.-T. (2021), "Augmented reality and virtual reality displays: Emerging technologies and future perspectives", *Light: Science & Applications*, No. 10, pp. 2-30, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41377-021-00658-8>.

Yang, H., Yu, J., Zo, H. and Choi, M. (2016), "User acceptance of wearable devices: An extended perspective of perceived value", *Telematics and Informatics*, Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 256–269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2015.08.007>.

Yen, Y.S. and Wu, F.S. (2016), "Predicting the adoption of mobile financial services: The impacts of perceived mobility and personal habit", *Computers in Human Behavior*, No. 65, pp. 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2015.08.007>.

Yim, M.Y.C., Chu, S.C. and Sauer, P.L. (2017), "Is Augmented Reality Technology an Effective Tool for E-commerce? An Interactivity and Vividness Perspective", *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, No. 39, pp. 89–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2017.04.001>.

Zeithaml, V.A. (1988), "Consumer Perceptions of Price, Quality, and Value: A Means-End Model and Synthesis of Evidence on JSTOR", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 52 No. 3, pp. 2–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224298805200302>.

Zheng, S. and Li, D. (2023), "The dark side of AR usage on customers' online purchase", *Nankai Business Review International*, Vol. 14 No. 1, pp. 128-160. <https://doi.org/10.1108/NBRI-03-2022-0023>